

Evaluating SDN applicability in the Edge

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Abstract—Multi-Access Edge computing (MEC) and Software Defined Networking (SDN) are novel paradigms, often utilised together, and aim to simplify the management of resources and offer cloud capabilities at the edge. SDN was originally designed for complex and large networks though recently found applications in smaller networks with fewer links. Little effort is given to the evaluation of SDN applicability at the Edge, especially in scenarios where Internet of Things (IoT) deployments are involved. This work presents an evaluation of SDN technology applicability at the edge in terms of data plane and control plane resource consumption. Our findings justify the wide acceptance of SDN and show that the control plane consumes relatively few resources compared to MEC resource pool. However, given the current trends of SDN, there are several possible improvements with respect to the cost of new equipment and the availability of tools.

Index Terms—Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), Software Defined Networking (SDN), Internet of Things (IoT)

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionised the way organisations operate by providing them with data abundance, a real-time and continuous stream of data. By adopting IoT, organisations are able to reduce operational costs, efficiently monitor their processes even in remote areas, and collect (near) real-time data to optimize their procedures [1]. Despite the benefits it brings, IoT also introduces several challenges in terms of the computational and storage-related capabilities of such devices. Both temporary and permanent storage of data is subject to security and privacy risks [2]. It is common for IoT devices to lack the computational power to perform complex tasks, like analysis and data encryption in order to minimize energy consumption.

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Transferring IoT data to the cloud may seem the most appealing approach, but taking a closer look reveals several problems and limitations. Data often need to traverse through multiple networks to reach the desired cloud point (data center), leading to increased overall delay and jitter. Privacy and confidentiality concerns also arise with large organisations like critical infrastructure operators being reluctant [3]. Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) is a novel paradigm that focuses on offering cloud features at the edge. MEC enables faster, more secure and cost-effective processing of data for IoT applications by bringing computing and storage resources closer to the edge of the network, thus providing a significant advantage over traditional cloud computing approaches.

Software Defined Networking (SDN) is considered the de-facto standard of designing and operating large and complex networks. In an SDN-based infrastructure, the control plane is decoupled from the data plane simplifying many processes. The networking devices are considered simple forwarding elements with little intelligence and high flexibility in terms of functionality [4]. The intelligence is instead present in a logically centralized software-driven control plane. This approach enables the control plane to hide data plane peculiarities and present the network as a unified software system allowing applications to interact with it through well-defined architectural styles like REpresentational State Transfer (REST) [5].

In this paper, an evaluation of SDN applicability at the network’s edge is carried out in order to showcase its benefits and limitations in MEC IoT environments. Through this work, the performance of data plane devices in terms of hardware resources consumption and controller computational resources consumption is measured. The structure of the paper is as follows:

- Section II presents works related to SDN application at the edge
- Section III presents the proposed system model, describing the evaluation architecture and offering details regarding the Access SDN controller.
- Section IV presents the evaluation methodology used and the obtained results.
- Section V summarises our findings and proposes future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Several attempts have been made in the past to integrate software-defined management approaches into other domains of Informatics and Communication Technologies (ICT). The

utilization of SDN technology at the Edge has been investigated in past years by several researchers [6]–[8]. Li et al. developed an edge caching mechanism that utilizes base stations as caching nodes and leverages SDN capabilities to efficiently load balance traffic and limit network congestion [9]. Content is cached in neighbouring base stations if the local base station has insufficient resources. To avoid network congestion the caching methods take advantage of SDN’s ability to collect network statistics and identify the appropriate base station to cache the content. The proposed method aims at minimizing the overall latency and takes into consideration the content migration overhead and was evaluated in a virtualised Edge-Cloud environment using virtual machines and OpenVSwitch while to manage the network the authors chose Floodlight SDN controller.

Authors in [10] propose an Edge-Cloud load balancing framework that is characterized by low response delay based on SDN called Service Orchestration and Data Aggregation (SODA). SODA partitions the network into three sections, namely, the Vehicle network layer (VNL), the Middle Route layer (MRL) and Data Centers Layer (DCL). The DCL is responsible to orchestrate the entire network and push new services to the underlying layers, while the MRL is responsible to perform efficient routing. Finally, the VNL consists of the Radio Access Network and mobile vehicles able to transmit and receive information from the CDL. Despite its flexibility, the proposed framework is optimized for mobile vehicles. Following a similar hierarchical approach, Ji et al [11] propose a three-tier system for vehicular networks that leverages SDN and MEC paradigms.

Similarly, in [12] the limitations of cloud-orchestrated networking services are described and a disaggregated SDN control plane emphasizing controller placement is proposed. After some initial experimentation with emulated topologies, the authors formulate the Edge Controller placement problem and prove it as an NP-Hard. The authors proceed in presenting 2 optimization algorithms, one for small-scale networks and one for larger-scale networks. Evaluation results in MATLAB simulations and in mininet topologies prove the efficiency of their solutions in terms of communications overhead and optimal solution calculation.

Authors in [13] propose a multi-layer MEC system approach able to integrate various IoT networks in the 5G cellular architecture. To optimally allocate computing resources the authors propose two energy-aware and latency-aware offloading algorithms. The first one is suitable for IoT networks whereas the second one is targeted towards D2D networks. The proposed system makes use of SDN technology at the core though it does not specify if SDN is utilised at the edge.

Rizawan et al propose a dynamic path selection algorithm for vehicular MEC environments [14]. Taking into consideration the time complexity of the problem the authors suggest a network partitioning scheme based on the divide-and-conquer method. Specifically, they propose two partitioning algorithms that consider resource placement and avoid unwanted paths during path construction calculations.

Fig. 1: Proposed System Model

The aforementioned works demonstrate several use cases of SDN application and contribution at the edge, such as fast service offloading, load-balancing or enhancing the edge-to-cloud communication continuum. Despite their significant contribution, these works often assume virtual topologies and mathematical formulations to provide results that lean towards the theoretical evaluation of performance indicators. Before realising these works in actual products and services, a fundamental question should be raised: ‘Is SDN applicable at the Edge?’

III. SDN APPLICABILITY AT THE NETWORK’S EDGE

Fig. 2: Evaluation testbed topology

The proposed System Model, depicted in Figure 1, presents a typical MEC environment consisting of a programmable switching fabric (i.e. OpenFlow switches or similar), one or

more MEC nodes able to fully or partially accommodate application services and multiple IoT devices connected directly or indirectly through Gateways. The MEC nodes may also assist IoT devices by acting as an intermediate between them and the internet and offering them computational resources.

Fig. 3: OpenFlow pipeline

The SDN controller of choice is described in detail in [15]. In brief, the Access SDN controller is based on the Ryu framework and it offers the custom pipeline, illustrated in Figure 3, consisting of four tables in total, configured according to the values of Table I. The first table (table 0) is dedicated to network management and monitoring protocols like Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP). Control plane services, like link delay estimation, may use this table too. The second table (table 1 according to the figure) handles network packets that may cause broadcast storms or flooding, contributing to unnecessary network load. The third table (table 2 according to the figure) is used as an Access Control List (ACL) and security policy enforcement preventing malicious hosts from communicating with benign ones. Finally, the fourth table (table 3 according to the diagram) performs the switching of legitimate traffic. Taking into consideration the need for fast lookups and near-zero delay tolerance, all tables are allocated to hardware resources. In particular, three out of four tables are allocated to Ternary Content Addressable Memory (TCAM), a complex silicon chip designed for fast and parallel memory lookup, whereas the remaining is configured as a Hash table. The first three tables can accommodate 1024 OpenFlow rule entries each whereas the last table can accommodate 2048 OpenFlow rule entries.

Fig. 4: SDN Controller load for each scenario

IV. EVALUATION PROCESS AND RESULTS

The evaluation process consists of two phases. The first one focuses on evaluating the ability of commodity data plane devices (i.e. OpenFlow switches) in handling IoT traffic, using

the proposed pipeline as described in Section III. The second phase aims at evaluating the control plane’s ability in handling various network sizes.

1) *Data Plane Evaluation:* The data plane evaluation experiments were executed using the testbed topology illustrated in Figure 2. Two Aruba 2930F 24 Gigabit with 4SFP 10Gbit port switches were utilised to evaluate data plane performance. Aruba 2930 series switches are considered a cost-efficient solution for access and edge environments with enough features to accommodate most MEC deployments. The ProVision ASIC can easily handle multi-gigabit loads supporting OpenFlow versions 1.0 and 1.3. A set of Raspberry Pis devices were used to emulate various IoT sensor devices generating UDP traffic. Finally, a high-end PC serves as the traffic sink receiving all IoT traffic. A simple custom traffic generator was developed in Python using the Scapy framework [16]. Finally, the SDN controller is hosted on a Desktop PC with a 12-core CPU and 8 GB of RAM.

TABLE I: Custom OpenFlow pipeline

Table Number.	0	1	2	3
Capacity	1024	1024	1024	2048
Table Type	Hash	TCAM	TCAM	TCAM
Usage	Control Plane Functions	Broadcast messages handling	Access Control List	Switching

The objective of the experiments is to evaluate the data plane’s ability to handle multiple network flows using the pipeline described previously. To achieve this, the number of hosts increases progressively, forcing the control plane to generate multiple OpenFlow rules and install them on data plane devices.

A total of four scenarios were executed, starting with 200 emulated devices and incrementally adding 200 devices in each scenario. The experimental results of OpenFlow rules installed on each switch are illustrated in Figure 4, whereas in Figure 5 the total CPU usage of the SDN Controller is depicted. The control plane installs 8 OpenFlow rules to build the pipeline forwarding logic and facilitate some control plane monitoring processes. Figure 5 shows that the number of OpenFlow commands installed is proportional to the number of hosts, while the number of rules does not exceed the limit of 2048 rules imposed by the pipeline configuration. On the control plane’s side Figure 4, the overall CPU usage average is 8%, with peak values reaching 16%. These values translate to the average usage of one and two physical cores respectively for the given testbed. Finally, the custom pipeline introduces zero delays to hosts when compared with the simple switch mode of the Aruba 2930 switch thanks to the TCAM memory. A newly connected host had an average of 1 msec delay in both pipelines (simple and custom).

2) *Control Plane Evaluation:* The control plane performance was evaluated through multiple OVS-based topologies using Mininet. For each network size, multiple tests were run and average values were calculated. Specifically, 10 tests were executed for each one of the scenarios. All topologies and

clients were randomly generated and placed using bidirectional links to connect them. Before each test was run, the current topology was tested for unreachable hosts due to link absence (i.e. the network is checked if partitioned). Information related to the number of data plane devices and hosts of each scenario is provided in Table II. The last column of the table presents the time required for all hosts to achieve end-to-end communication.

The results of Table II show that the time required for all hosts to communicate with their peers is proportional to the network size. As the network size increases the control plane requires more time to install commands and compute new routes. OpenFlow was used as the protocol of communication between the control plane and the data plane.

TABLE II: Control Plane evaluation scenarios

Scenario	# switches	# hosts	duration (seconds)
1	10	20	6.35
2	20	20	7.18
3	50	20	9.62
4	100	20	25.6

The control plane resources consumption, and most importantly CPU usage, were constantly monitored and recorded in each scenario. Figure 6 presents the minimum, average, maximum and standard deviation of measurements of CPU usage of the Access SDN controller for the case of each scenario. The CPU load increases with the network size in terms of minimum, average, maximum and standard deviation values since the control planes have a larger search space to cover.

Fig. 5: Number of rules installed on Aruba switches for each scenario

V. CONCLUSION

SDN technology has a lot to offer in terms of statistics, flexibility and robustness of the MEC paradigm. several works were analysed in order to identify application scenarios

In this work, an evaluation of SDN applicability at an edge networking paradigm was carried out. Based on a simple yet general enough architecture, a basic testbed was created where

Fig. 6: Control Plane performance in various networking infrastructure sizes

several experiments were carried out focusing on the data plane’s capacity in terms of rules and processing delays and the control plane’s ability to handle larger and more complex network topologies.

In the future we aim to evaluate more SDN Controller like ONOS [17] and its newer version μ ONOS. There are over 30 SDN controllers available to this day [18], though few of them have been evaluated for Edge cases. Moreover, many of these controllers lack modern features and offer limited support for newer functionality.

In recent years the higher level of network programmability is made possible through data plane programming technologies and languages such as eBPF/XDP or P4 [19]. These technologies, often in the form of C-like language, allow the network operator to fully program the behaviour of forwarding devices and even manipulate packets in a previously impossible manner without sacrificing throughput [20]. Despite their benefits, equipment that supports these features is still expensive for Edge environments. Research efforts should focus on lowering the overall costs of these devices and also evaluate their potential benefits for such environments.

Finally, efforts should also focus on evaluating the performance of SDN as a policy enforcement engine in edge networks. While multiple applications can use the Access SDN Controller’s interface simultaneously, they might have contradicting demands. Taking into account the limited resources of the Edge, smart and efficient methods suitable for such an environment should be devised and validated.

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